

**MODERN ARCHITECTURAL SOLUTIONS OF MAHALLA AND
GUZARS**

Sereeva Guljazira Adilbaevna

Tashkent University of Architecture and Construction

senior lecturer of the "Urban Planning" department (Uzbekistan)

Tel.: (93) 804-83-11, e-mail: sereyeva.72@gmail.com

Annotation: *This article shows that the principle of "Mahalla", which is a unique form of self-government of the population, has not lost its significance and is being rapidly redeveloped. It was suggested that after independence, the role of mahallas in building civil society in the republic should be greater, and its content and functions should be expanded to create a new type of mahalla guzars with expanded content, structure and architecture. The aim is to find solutions for the design of modern architecture and room interiors based on historical traditions in the formation of mahalla guzars.*

Keywords: *urban planning, city, principles, "prosperous neighborhood" program, neighborhood, guzar, architectural structure, functional-planning structure, interior solutions.*

Introduction: Improving the living conditions of the urban and rural population of the Republic of Uzbekistan in a broad sense is an issue of great social and economic importance and is one of the important directions of the policy of our country.

A number of socio-economic issues of urban development are being solved in the modern development of large historical cities of the Republic of

Uzbekistan. The most fair social space, which fully takes into account human interests and rights, and realizes his age-old dreams and hopes, is the community of the neighborhood, which is considered a civil society. In addition to this, the development of the cities of Uzbekistan is promoting a number of urgent problems related to the formation of the structure of the current residential areas.

These are the expansion of the functional and planning structures of residential and public buildings, residential areas, neighborhoods, architectural and artistic design based on the traditions of urban planning that have been formed for centuries, and the community living of our people, the land - neighborhood, neighborhood. such as national traditions and increasing their effectiveness, Uzbekistan is related to urban development, natural climatic conditions and other specific aspects [1, p. 1.].

It should be noted that in the historical cities of Uzbekistan (Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara) in the course of their centuries-old development, unique principles of urban planning - mahalla, guzar, dakha and mavze - emerged in the formation of their functional and planning structures. The development of these principles based on the requirements of the present time, the formation and implementation of national traditions, and the improvement of the functional and planning structures of the cities of Uzbekistan, especially residential areas. For this reason, the development of traditional principles of urban planning - neighborhood, guzar, dacha and mavze - in the modern conditions, national and practical implementation is considered one of the urgent problems of the republican urban planning.

Materials and methods: In addition, Uzbekistan will participate in the Venice Biennale of Architecture for the first time. It introduces the neighborhood to the world.

Uzbekistan From May 22 to November 21, 2021, a large-scale event in the world of architecture and art - XVII - International Biennale of Architecture will

be held in Venice, where Uzbekistan will present its national project: "Neighborhood : the life of the city and region" will be shown. The national pavilion of Uzbekistan is located at the intersection of the main places of the Biennale - "Arsenal" and "Giardini", and will border the host Italian pavilion. Uzbekistan, a debutant country, will present its "Neighborhood: City and Regional Life" project for the first time [3, p. 6].

He also emphasized the importance of preserving these neighborhoods as cultural heritage. "All the work done will help to preserve the collection of information and this is an opportunity to pass on the life history of our ancestors to our children.

These values are reflected in the project of the National Pavilion. The concept of the exhibition "Neighbourhood: City and Regional Life" tells about the community structure that exists not only in Uzbekistan, but also shows the unique characteristics of Uzbek society [2, p. 18]. Neighborhoods have regional, customs, climate and different forms, and historically they were built on the basis of family ties. Architectural features, the neighborhood is a whole social structure that has acquired a hereditary basis, and this phenomenon must be preserved in any way.

"We are incredibly lucky, because Tashkent is the only city in the Muslim East where its settlements have been filmed, so the Mahalla: City and Regional Life project will have a solid documentary foundation.

"The Venice Architecture Biennale provides a unique context to address contemporary themes and reflections on planning and the future of architecture. This national work is embedded in a vibrant and productive intellectual environment, an International International Conference aimed at creating new networks, exploring other contexts and creating new content. it is possible to learn new ways of representing Uzbekistan and use cultural exchange through feedback on the intellectual scene [3, p. 7].

Project documents are determined by the spatial qualities of neighborhood

conditions, changes in time and stagnation. Participants of the research laboratory of the center of modern art, which has the task of developing modern art and cultural practice in Uzbekistan, will actively participate in the task. They collect materials on the ground, conduct surveys among residents and restore the portrait of the neighborhoods of the past years, while updating the maps. Of course, the neighborhood - the whole social structure in terms of architectural features and these offices should be preserved in any way.

From the beginning of the development process of the neighborhood system to the present, the sub-districts serving the lifestyle of the city residents have been of great importance. Currently, as before, the neighborhood houses serve as a functional and compact center for the population. In these events, the social life of the residents of the neighborhood is reflected. Neighborhood houses are often located at pedestrian-traffic intersections. Neighborhood houses are distinguished by their convenience, versatility and comprehensiveness. The combination of functional features and compositional solution is reflected here.

Such facilities create favorable conditions for meeting the basic needs of the population and families in their daily life. The location of neighborhood residents is related to the construction of the city and its functional function. Neighborhoods that do not have shopping malls form an empty, semi-open composition from the point of view of architectural construction, while shopping malls located on pedestrian routes form the basis of the city center.

At the same time, relevant ministries and agencies were assigned the task of providing farm and household appliances for neighborhood residents and teahouses at preferential prices, providing small enterprises under the management of the fund with the necessary tools, spare parts, and semi-finished products of raw materials. It is trying to bring the social and cultural service sector to the residents of the neighborhood closer to the residences, to make the server service colorful, to organize it at the level of the cultural needs and demands of

the citizens. As a non-governmental organization, the foundation provides close support to local authorities in holding cultural events in neighborhoods, providing household services, beautifying pedestrian areas, improving communal services, and providing residents with water and gas. In the following years, bakeries, kitchens, dry cleaners, shoe repair shops, trade shops were created in the neighborhoods, and these measures are aimed at improving the social and cultural life of the population and raising their standard of living. Based on the single architectural project "Modern neighborhood":

Residents' apartments in the neighborhoods are made to have the same appearance depending on the location of the multi-story buildings;

Inner streets, sidewalks, roadside ditches and road barriers will be overhauled.

Picture. New central guzars in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In order to improve the material technical base, the buildings of the neighborhood assembly are being reconstructed and new neighborhood houses are being built (picture), they are provided with computer equipment. In particular, on the example of the city of Tashkent, "Neighborhood centers" are being built and commissioned in each district. It is intended to ensure the stability of families and prevent the crime of young people, especially women, in cooperation with the neighborhood assembly and all social sector organizations.

It is noteworthy that in the current "Prosperous neighborhood" state program, it is planned to increase the volume of consumer loans given by commercial banks to the population for the purchase of household appliances and household equipment, and to build multi-storey houses in the regions of our country at the expense of mortgage loans. Also, it is noteworthy that beauty salons for women are being organized in every district [1, 2-p].

Discussion: Of course, these considerations are reflected in the number of community centers and libraries that are growing in all regions and neighborhoods, and the number of places of interest that residents and students are losing. In each of his speeches, the head of state places special emphasis on youth education, reading, talent discovery and support. This encourages each of us to wake up, realize that we are responsible for our own lives, and urges us to take immediate action. After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, our government special attention is being paid to the restoration of traditional neighborhoods, increasing their importance in the life of our society [1, 2-p.]. During the past period, a lot of work was carried out in the cities and villages of the Republic on the formation of neighborhoods and their development.

There are 3 types of neighborhood residents:

Neighborhood in historical areas;

Individually planned, i.e., low-rise residential areas in the area of the neighborhood;

Multi-storied buildings, that is, in micro-districts, there is a neighborhood.

From ancient times, the neighborhood was considered a special public place, where there was an elder and mirab administration, a mosque, green gardens and teahouses with ponds and mud floors.

Local mosques, schools and madrassas, pools, teahouses, trade stalls, and green markets were located in large and rich neighborhoods. The residents of the neighborhood with a small or profitable population had only a small pool, and

sometimes a small tea house with greenery.

The results of the study of neighborhood service objects show that by the 20th century it was necessary to build additional mosques and small houses. Usually, the neighborhoods have crafts and trade, as well as a cultural center, and they are called Guzars. Guzars are located on major highways or at intersections of such roads. Guzars had various public places, including a large mosque, a madrasah, a caravanserai, a teahouse, a blacksmith's shop, a barber shop, a mill, a slaughterhouse, stalls, and a small market. These guzars served the passengers, as well as the residents of the neighboring neighborhood. Guzars performed an important task of uniting neighborhoods into a large single area. According to the structure of the city, the territorial area of the neighborhood was different. In the areas near the city center, the population density was 350-400 people per hectare, and the neighborhood area was 1-2 hectares. In remote areas, sometimes it was 15-20 hectares [p. 4, 34-35].

As a result of historical research of Tashkent city neighborhoods (Yangi Beltepa, Zafar Abod, Suzuk Ota, Namuna) from a historical point of view, specific aspects of the organization of neighborhood activities in these neighborhoods were determined.

In addition, the neighborhood paid attention to the education of the young generation. Neighborhood affairs were discussed at residents' meetings. In the life of the neighborhood, elderly people were treated with great attention and respect, and elderly elders were consulted on issues of lifestyle and education. As a result of respect for the elderly, a special room for the elderly was formed in the neighborhood, and they are often located close to the teahouse.

Result: The results of the research show that public and trade centers in the area of the neighborhood were created during many centuries in the process of rational distribution of the construction of service centers in populated areas and "natural selection".

In the architectural solutions of the residents of the neighborhood, the main attention is focused on the historical plan with its favorable conditions. Because mostly older elders and neighborhood activists work there. The rooms are placed taking into account their youth. Depending on the types of neighborhood centers, if they consist of one or two floors, the following rooms, which are used a lot, are placed mainly on the first floor:

- the room of the chairman of the neighborhood committee;
- neighborhood committee secretary's room;
- women's counselor's room;
- room of senior police inspector, etc.

In the future, the following should be paid attention to when designing neighborhood houses: The architectural structure of the neighborhood building should have a harmonious appearance with the surrounding buildings. It is desirable to organize recreation zones of the neighborhood not only for the elderly, but also for women, young people and children, to place separate corridors, restaurants, teahouses, clubs and playgrounds in them.

Taking into account the religious and social background of the population, separate teahouses should be set aside for men and women to have cultural leisure, cultural houses and clubs should be established in harmony with the national and modern harmony of the population. It is worth mentioning that, in the neighborhood, libraries, national craft clubs, sports halls, which serve to educate the youth of the neighborhood in a spiritual way, to spend their free time in a meaningful way, and to make the growing young generation healthy and they are of great importance in perfect education.

There is a children's playground in the street part of the neighborhood courtyard. The courtyard is decorated with verandas providing cool weather, fountains in the center and landscape design. The children's playground has gymnastic equipment, swings, a sandpit, and interesting attractions.

Neighborhood houses are national and modern, mainly wood, national patterns carved into ganch (plaster), glass and high-quality materials are used in the interior. Another convenience aspect of the project is equipped with modern equipment and facilities. Using the Modern style to create a design environment, soft light colors and equipment in the interior can attract people of both young and old age (Fig. 2). In the interior, walls and ceilings are made of national ganches and figures in a modern style.

On the ceilings, the main modern simple lighting fixtures, i.e. halogens, provided a high level of room lighting. The exterior of the building was made of bricks, marble, iron and wood materials. Aerated bricks can be used in walls to increase their strength and resistance to weather conditions.

Iron materials are used in the columns, marbles are used in the entrance staircase, and wood is used in the carving of national motifs on the window edges. These materials provide long-term strength and durability in buildings and interiors under any conditions. Gray and light brown colors were used on the exterior of the building.

Conclusion: the populated areas of the historical cities of Uzbekistan acquired a unique structure during the long-term development process. The process of formation of their structure took place in a natural way, based on the principle of expediency. At each stage of development, the principle of expediency required people to follow certain construction laws. As a result, the structures of the historical cities were formed that correspond to the natural and climatic conditions of the populated areas, the lifestyle of the population, aesthetic and other requirements.

The accumulation of centuries-old experiences and their passing from generation to generation led to the formation of traditional neighborhoods, guzars, dachas and mavzes. These are a unique type of self-management, characteristic of the structure of cities and villages of Uzbekistan.

During the past long historical period, the neighborhood type of self-management of the population shows that it is viable.

In the "Old City" part of Tashkent city, historically formed neighborhoods, in the districts formed by private houses based on the plan since the second half of the 19th century, in the micro-districts consisting of multi-storey residential buildings, neighborliness, neighborliness and other traditions are still preserved today. remains, at the same time, they are being enriched with new functions based on the requirements of the times [5, p. 28].

Currently, the importance of the role of self-government bodies in the establishment of civil society in our republic, the fact that the state is paying serious attention to this issue, the enrichment of the content and functions of the neighborhoods, the expansion of their scope of authority, the content of the neighborhoods has been enriched, It requires the creation of well-equipped new type of residential buildings with modern and national style, beautiful architecture and interior solutions.

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